

Interest Rate Deregulation and Loans and Advances of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: *This study examined the effect of interest rate deregulation on Nigerian banking system. The study adopted Augmented Dickey – Fuller (ADF), Bound test and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). The correlation result indicated that of the correlation matrix that all the explanatory variables (interest rate, lending rate and deposit rate) had effect on loan and advances. The results of the unit root test revealed that interest rate and lending rate were stationary at level 1(0) while loan and advances and deposit rate were stationary at first difference 1(1). Also the results of the bound test revealed that there exist long run equilibrium relationship among the variables. The result of the ARDL indicated that interest rate had significant effect on loan and advances while lending rate and deposit rate had an insignificant effect on loan and advances. It was concluded that banks should monitor the level of loan and advances in respect to major ratios for effective performance. The study thus, recommended that banks should monitor lending rate which should be fixed in order to enhance lending performance. Regulatory authority should ensure that macroeconomic variables such as money supply, liquidity ratio, lending rate, monetary policy rate are effectively managed to enhance bank performance.*

Key Words: Deposit Rate, Deregulation, Interest Rate, Lending Rate and Loans and Advances

I. Introduction

Banking sector of an economy still remains the most heavily regulated and monitored system due to the critical role the sector plays in national growth and development through the channeling of investible resources for productive purpose which has over reaching effect on the economy. As a result of this significant role played by banks, many regulatory and reforms framework have been initiated by developing countries in order to further strengthen and consolidate their activities so as to be highly competitive both locally and internationally. The regulation of interest rate by monetary authority has been of great importance because interest rate serves as a major determinant of investment.

Interest rate is the rate that is paid on either savings or lending. It represents the rate of return that is due to the owner of funds for differing present consumption for future consumption (Makinde, 2016). Generally, interest rate performs the function of efficiently allocating limited available financial resources for investment purpose and could be tailored to respond to the developmental need of an economy.

Banks are the main intermediary in the financial sector due to their ability to poll large amount of savings from surplus unit and channeled them to the investment sector in form of lending. Bank lending is of great significant because it allows business enterprisers and government at all level to undertake investment and productive activities which promote growth and development (Felicia, 2011). However, the

level of interest rate may determine the extent at which banks perform their lending activities because banks rely on low saving rate and lending rate to make profit.

During inflationary period interest rate may be adopted to discourage savings and borrowing thereby discouraging investment while low interest rate is adopted to stimulate investment through encouragement of savings and borrowings. However, banks are able to make profit and enhance performance through interest rate spread which is the difference between lending rate and savings rate. Thus, the mala-management of interest rate policy by the Central Bank of a country could negatively affect the overall performance of financial institutions which will retard the growth and development of the economy (CBN, 2015).

Financial sector was highly regulated before the adoption of Structural Adjusted Programme (SAP) in Nigeria. During this period interest rate was fixed by monetary authorities in line with the prevailing economic conditions. However, the adoption of Structural Adjusted Programme (SAP) brought the market based determinants of interest rate by the demand and supply for loanable funds in order to foster the growth and development of developing countries.

In 1986, the Structural Adjusted Programme (SAP) was introduced in Nigeria to deregulate interest rate and exchange rate. Interest rate was allowed to be determined by the interaction between the force of demand and supply and the players in the financial market were lenders and borrowers are allowed to negotiate the rate of deposits and lending with the purpose of promoting effectiveness and efficiency in intermediation process, ensure healthy competition and greater participation (Abogan, Olajide & Oloba, 2014).

In Nigeria, the deregulation of interest rate is met by mix reactions by expert and scholars. Some of the scholars believe that interest rate deregulation has the propensity to affect investment drastically due to high rate on lending (Abiodun, 1987; Ojo, 1989). Iklide (1990) go against this notion and proposed that interest rate deregulation will not only correct the financial repression policy but will also encourage high savings through high deposit rate. Deposit money banks play important role in the mobilization of resources and allocation of funds to the productive sector (Victor & Richard, 2013). However, the prevailing interest rate will determines the effectiveness of lending of banks which determine

While many scholars have delved into the issue of deregulation and banks performance little research still exist in the field of the study. The major gaps in the previous studies are that they ignore some macroeconomic variables such as loan to deposit ratio, lending rate and deposit rate which are major indicators of banking sector activities. Also, most of the study suffers methodology deficiency, in that they failed to consider the stationarity of variables employed and the relationships which exist among these variables. It is noted this methodological deficiency could greatly affect the results of the study thereby leading to wrong conclusions. In lieu to the above analysis, this study thus examined the effect of interest rate deregulations on the Nigerian banking sector. The other part of this paper is divided into literatures review, methods, interpretation of analysis and conclusion.

II. Literature Review

Interest rate represents a percentage that is usually charged on sum of amount that is given to borrower for the usage of such money with the promise to pay back in future date. According to Ojo (2001), interest rates are defined as the rental payments for the use of credit by borrowers or the return for parting with liquidity by lenders. Obute, Adyorough and Itodo (2012) defined interest rate deregulation as a situation whereby interest rate is determined by the forces of demand and supply. Okiri (2016) stressed that when banks pay deposit rate on deposits mobilized and charged lending rate on lending to customers. However, the spread between lending rate and deposit rate determines the level of performance of banks which influence the lending activities of banks.

There are many literatures that studied the effect of interest rate on banking activities. A study by Anthony (2012) investigated the determinants of bank savings in Nigeria as well as on Nigeria's economic

growth from 1970-2006 by adopting Distributed Lag-Error Correction Model (DL-ECM) and Distributed Model and it was revealed Financial Deepening (FSD), Interest Rate Spread (IRS) had positive influence on GDP per capita. Also, Akabom-Ita (2012) examined the impact of interest rate on net assets of multinational companies in Nigeria from 1995 – 2010 and it was revealed that an increase in interest rate results in reduction in net assets of banks. Furthermore, Okoye and Richard (2013) found that lending rate and monetary policy rate had significant and positive effects on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks by examining the impact of bank lending rate on the performance of Nigerian Deposit Money Banks between 2000 and 2010 using secondary and analyzed using regression technique. Similarly, Enyioko (2012) employed twenty (20) banks to examine the performances of banks and interest rate policies and found that interest rate policies have not improved the overall performances of banks significantly.

Ugwuanyi (2012) examined interest rate deregulation and bank lending in Nigeria within the period of 1987 to 2011 using ordinary least square (OLS) techniques. The study found that lending rate, cash reserve ratio, total bank deposit and gross domestic product have different degree of relationship on Bank Lending and Advances (BLA). By adopting Simple linear regression technique, Onwumere, Okore and Ibe (2012) studied the impact of interest rate liberalization on savings and investment in Nigeria from 1976 to 1999 and it was revealed that interest rate liberalization had negative and insignificant impact on savings.

Ene *et al.*, (2015) empirically examined the effect of interest rates deregulation on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria between 1986 and 2014 using OLS regression method. The study indicated that high interest rates increase the performance of deposit money banks. Also, the study of Sanya (2015) indicated that banking sector reforms had no effect on banks performance and the Nigerian economy.

Ekong and Udonwa (2015) investigated the performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria after Banking Sector Reforms using Error Correction Mechanism and Chow test over the period 1970-2012 and it was found that the reforms lead to improvement in performance of banks. Akiri (2016) examined the effect of financial liberalization on the profitability of deposit money banks (DMBS) in Nigeria using time series annual data from the period 1975-2013. The result of the OLS indicated that financial liberalization in Nigeria improved profitability. Also, Makinde (2016) examined effect of interest rate on commercial bank deposits in Nigeria using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression techniques and the findings indicated negative relationship between the interest rates and the commercial bank deposits in Nigeria. Akinkunmi (2017) employed panel data to examine the effect of internal regulation from monetary authority on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria by applying Stochastic Frontier Analysis and it was indicated that regulation had negative and significant impact on the total cost of bank.

III. Methods

The study employed descriptive and analytical research method to explain the relationships that exist between the dependent variable (proxied as loan and advances) and the independent variables (proxied as interest rate, deposit rate and lending rate). Data used were mainly time series data which range from 1986 to 2016 and obtained from Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin (2016).

Model Specification

The model for this study followed the empirical model of Ugwuanyi (2012) and Ene *et al.*, (2015).

This is formulated as:

$$LAD = f(\text{INTR}, \text{LR}, \text{DR})$$

Where:

LAD = Loan and Advances

INTR = Interest Rate

LR = Lending Rate

DR = Deposit Rate

This can be written mathematically given as:

$$LDR = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \text{INTR} + \lambda_2 \text{LR} + \lambda_3 \text{DR} + \epsilon$$

Where:

λ_0 = Constant term

λ_1 - λ_3 = Coefficient of Parameter

ϵ = Stochastic error term

The study employed Augmented-Dick-Fuller (ADF) units root test to test the stationarity level of the macroeconomic in other to avoid nonsense regression while the Bound Co-integration test was employed to assess the long run relationship among the macroeconomic variables. Also, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) is employed to ascertain the speed of adjustment from the short run equilibrium to the long run equilibrium state. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method is preferable to other co-integration techniques because it has the capacity to combine variables with 1(1) or combination of 1(1) and 1(0). Also, the technique offers robust result by mitigating the problem of endogeneity in that it recognizes the dependent variable and independent variables (Pesaran & Shin 1999). Also, it is suitable for sample with low observation.

In order to test the reliability and robustness of the regression results, the study adopted various diagnostics test which include, Normality test, Serial Correlation Lagrange Multiplier Test, Breuch Pagan test for Heteroscedacity and Cusum Stability test

IV. Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Correlation Matrix

Table 1 Correlation Matrix Result

	LAD	INTR	LR	DR
LAD	1.000000			
INTR	-0.431028	1.000000		
LR	-0.345602	0.658923	1.000000	
DR	-0.604511	0.443669	0.499599	1.000000

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

Table q shows the correlation matrix for the macroeconomic variables employed in this study and indicated the absence of multicollinearity among variables since the correlation values are less 70%. It could be seen for the results of the correlation matrix that all the explanatory variables (interest rate, lending rate and deposit rate) have negative correlation with loan and advances with deposit rate having strong negative correlation value of -60%, interest rate having moderate correlation value of -43% and finally lending rate having weak correlation value of -34%.

Test of Stationarity for the Variables

Table 2: Summary of Unit Root Test

VARIABLES	TEST STATISTIC	5% CRITICAL VALUE	Prob.	LEVEL	S/NS
LAD	/3.979646/	/3.587527/	0.0221	1(1)	S
INTR	/3.940821/	/3.587527/	0.0240	1(0)	S
LR	/5.819927/	/3.603202/	0.0004	1(0)	S
DR	/6.071431/	/3.574244/	0.0001	1(1)	S

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

Table 2 above revealed that interest rate and lending rate were stationary at level 1(0) while loan and advances and deposit rate were stationary at first difference 1(1). However, since the macroeconomic variables employed are mixture of I(0) and I(1) orders variables thus the study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag of short run and long run equilibrium

Long Run Relationship

Table 3: Bound Test

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	7.279512	3
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.01	3.1
5%	2.45	3.63
2.5%	2.87	4.16
1%	3.42	4.84

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

Table 3 showed the result of the long run association-ship among the macroeconomic variables using the bound test and indicated that the F-statistics value is 7.279512 which is greater than the critical value of 2.45 of upper bound (I0) at 5% level of significance. Thus, it was indicated that interest rate, lending rate and deposit rate have long run equilibrium relationship with loan and advances during deregulation period.

Interpretation of Model Results

Table 4: Short Run Co-integration Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(INTR)	0.025181	0.008705	2.892692	0.0078
D(LR)	-0.013612	0.007418	-1.835008	0.0784
D(DR, 2)	-0.045704	0.020205	-2.262028	0.0326
CointEq(-1)	-1.052626	0.278367	-3.781427	0.0009

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

Table 4 showed and short run result. The result of the short run co-integration result revealed that there is speed of adjustment among the macroeconomic variables with a negative and significant value of -1.052626. This implies that loan and advances will adjust back to equilibrium at 105% in the short run. Also, in the short run it is revealed that only interest rate has a positive significant impact on loan ad advances while lending rate and deposit rate having significant negative effect on loan and advances in the short run.

Table 5: Long Run Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INTR	0.023922	0.007028	3.404052	0.0022
LR	-0.012931	0.006949	-1.860997	0.0745
D(DR)	-0.043419	0.011081	-3.918272	0.0006

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

The result of the long run relationship revealed that interest rate had a positive and significant effect on load and advances in Nigeria with a coefficient of 0.023922, implying that an increase in INTR will lead to increases in loan and advances. Also, lending rate was establish to have significance and negative effect on loan and advances with a coefficient value of -0.012931 which means that an increase in lending rate will lead fall in loan and advances.

Finally, the long run ARDL model reveals that there is significant an indirect significant relationship between deposit rate and loan and advances with a coefficient value of -0.043419 which implies that a percentage increase in money supply will result in fall in loan and advances.

Post Test Techniques

Table 6: Diagnostics Results

Diagnostics test	Observed Value	P-value (Chi-square)
Normality Test	0.470303	0.7905
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for autocorrelation	1.531201	0.4651
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	5.493280	0.2403
Ramsey RESET Test	0.430834	0.5178

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2018

Table 6 above shows the diagnostics test for the regression result to check the reliability and robustness of the regression model. The Jarque-Bera normality test revealed that the residual of the model is normally distributed since the P value is insignificant at 5% level of. Also, Breusch-Godfrey Lagranger Multiplier test (LM) revealed that the regression model is not serially correlated since the p-value of 0.4651 is greater than 5% conventional level. The result of Breusch-pegan test gives a probability value of 0.2403 which is greater than at 5% critical value thus leading to the acceptance of null hypotheses that the residual is homosecedatic. Finally, the result revealed that there is no misspecification in the regression model as revealed by the Ramsey Reset Test with a probability value of 0.5178 thus leasing to the acceptance of the null hypothesis

V. Conclusion

Interest rate plays a significant role on the banking sector. This study is of great significant due to the important role of banks loan and advances in Nigeria. For the banks to balance their main objectives of liquidity, profitability and solvency, lending must be handled effectively and the banks must behave in a way that there potential customers are attracted and retained. Thus, this study examined the effect of interest rate deregulation on Nigerian banking system.

The study found that interest rate has significant effect on loan and advance and an increase in interest rate will result in increase in loan and advances. The study revealed that banks liquidity ratio and deposit rate reduces loan and advances as they increase. The implication of these findings is that banks performance in terms of their loan and advances reacted to major changes in their macroeconomic variables like interest rate, liquidity ratio and deposit rate. Thus, it is concluded that banks should monitor their level of loan and advances in respect to their major ratios for effective performance. The study thus, recommended that banks should monitor lending rate and should be fixed in way to enhanced lending performance. Regulatory authority should ensure the macroeconomic variables such as money supply, liquidity ratio, maximum lending rate, monetary policy rate are effectively managed to enhance bank performance.

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